

DIRECTING HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS TO LEARN ARTISTIC VALUES

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Abstract. *The article is directed to the study of artistic values by students of higher pedagogic education, and the issue of promotion of creative ideas through artistic values is highlighted.*

Keywords: *Artistic, intellectual idea, creative, mental movement, aesthetic sophistication, artistic ability, heuristic.*

INTRODUCTION

In the decision PD-5040 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 26.03.2021 "On measures to radically improve the system of spiritual and educational affairs", as a result of the comprehensive reforms and creative works implemented in our country, the way of thinking and worldview of our people is fundamentally changing "From national revival to national on the basis of the life-giving idea "toward the rise" is gaining more and more importance. However, despite all the efforts made, there are still problems that hinder spiritual and educational reforms. These are:

- that there is no integrated system in the organization of spiritual and educational processes;
- it is possible to cite as an example that insufficient organizational-practical and scientific-research work is being carried out to protect young people from moral threats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to solve existing problems and increase the efficiency and effectiveness of spiritual and educational work, in order to solve the existing problems in the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 26.03.2021 "On measures to fundamentally improve the system of spiritual and educational work":

- turning a healthy outlook and creativity into a national movement in society;
- ensuring continuity of spiritual education in family, educational organizations and neighborhoods;
- strengthening the ideological immunity of young people against ideological and informational attacks;
- achieving priority of moral and ethical standards, national and universal values in culture, literature, cinema, theater, music and all types of art, publishing and printing products, mass media;
- effective ideological struggle against terrorism, extremism, human trafficking, drug business and other dangerous threats are defined as the priority areas of fundamental improvement of the system of spiritual and educational work;
- development of effective and effective propaganda technologies and methods of spiritual and educational activities;
- study of foreign experience in organizing spiritual-educational and educational work, as well as detailed analysis and evaluation of today's ideological processes from a scientific-practical point of view;
- to carry out monitoring of spiritual-educational and educational work in the area of pre-school education, general secondary, secondary special and higher education system, neighborhood and other structures, development of scientifically based educational technologies, proposals and recommendations for solving identified problems;

organization of fundamental, practical and innovative research on spiritual education and social and humanitarian sciences, coordination of their implementation in practice.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Value is a concept used to show the universal, socio-ethical, cultural and spiritual significance of certain events in reality. All things that are important for man and humanity, such as freedom, peace, justice, social equality, enlightenment, truth, goodness, beauty, material and spiritual wealth, tradition, customs, etc. are Values. In any field of social sciences, research on value has been carried out, they have tried to define this concept in this way.

According to J. Tulenov, in everyday life, in the eyes of many people, things (for example, valuables, jewelry), natural phenomena, social events, demands in society, dreams and hopes, traditions and ceremonies, cultural assets, etc. are understood as values. Values are divided into several types according to their nature. For example, man and his life are considered the highest value. There are several values in human life. In particular, national value, natural value, spiritual value and artistic values, etc.

Meaning of artistic word:

1 Express reality through elegant art tools, methods, images

doer; Fiction. A work of art. Fine art. Life is the essence of fiction film and fiction.

2 Belonging to art. Artistic skill. Artistic image. Artistic thinking. Artistic taste.

Artistic potential. For example, only intention is not enough in creativity, artistic potential and deep thought are also needed. From the newspaper. Artistic thought is born with its form. U. Normatov, Talent education.

3. Creative activity related to artistic creation. Artistic director, artistic amateurs, artistic team.

An intellectual idea.....

Creativity...

Mental act.....

Aesthetic sophistication.....

Artistic talent...

HEURISTICS (Greek peshtzko - I look for, I find)

1) special methods of problem solving (heuristic methods). The opposite of solving the problem by relying on precise mathematical models and using traditional methods. The use of heuristic methods significantly reduces the time to solve the problem. The solution obtained in this way is not considered the most correct solution, but one of the possible solutions. Most of the time, the goal set by using Heuristics cannot be achieved. Sometimes in the psychological and cybernetic literature, heuristics are understood as inductive methods of problem solving;

2) Method of creating programs for EHM (computer) (heuristic programming). If the programmer is ready to solve the problem in the way of creating simple programs. method to EHM

coding in an "understandable" form, in heuristic programming it seeks to form an intuitive (feeling) understandable method of solving a problem. This method also does not allow an absolute solution to the task;

3) organization of productive creative thinking (thinking) process (heuristic activity);

4) a subject that studies heuristic activity; a special branch of the science of

thinking. As a science, it develops as a mixture of the subjects of psychology, theory of artificial intelligence, structural linguistics, information theory;

5) a special teaching method (Socratic dialogues) or problem solving. Additional questions and examples are provided to guide learners. Participants give guiding questions, examples, and counter-examples to the author of the idea while solving complex problems.

Artistic value nourishes the human mind both materially and spiritually. Artistic aesthetic sophistication, like works of beauty, embodies the world of sophistication in the human mind.

Artistic consciousness, like forms of social consciousness, in certain periods, due to its relative independence, can be actively influenced to fundamentally change some of the essences that form the basis of society. Artistic value plays a major role in the manifestation of the student's will. In the formation of artistic value in students, their nationalism, historical events, love for the culture of the past, and feelings of national pride are manifested. It can be concluded that it is appropriate to develop artistic values on the basis of national ideology based on social, economic, political and moral factors.

It is necessary for students to be able to do the following in the formation of artistic values.

- performing types of artistic analysis and ways of applying them to the work;
- to be able to thoroughly analyze the work of art;
- experiences of world literature and literary studies to national literature
- know how to apply;
- to understand the history of artistic analysis methods;
- to be able to analyze all types of works.

CONCLUSION

The study of artistic skills improves the literary and aesthetic thinking of students, develops their heuristic and creative abilities, and helps them to make scientific observations. Also, we read Cholpon's "literature in its true sense, to give spirit to a dead, faded, extinguished, wounded heart, clean water of enlightenment that cleans not only our body, but the black mud that has soaked into our blood, washes away the dirt of the sharp heart, and makes our cloudy windows bright and clear, dust and soil. We should be able to convey the importance and relevance of artistic ideas such as spring water that cleanses our tired eyes from childhood. In the direction of artistic values, it is appropriate to conduct an experimental test among students and popularize it. It is necessary to introduce the formation of artistry based on the final conclusions of the experimental test in the lessons. It is necessary to develop the experimental test program in the form of tests and promote them.

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